

Quantifying Uncertainty in Image Captioning

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Abstract

There has been much hype in large language models with limited proof that these models deliver what is needed or expected. We set out to quantify uncertainty in image captioning models considering structured captions. We propose an information theoretic method to quantify aleatoric uncertainty. The aim of this study is to assess the relationship between falsification, caption complexity and uncertainty. We find longer captions to have higher falsification and aleatoric uncertainty with a decrease in performance. We also consider data shift by adding noise to our images and find that there was little effect on the aleatoric uncertainty.

Key Words: Information theory, large language models, uncertainty quantification

1. Introduction

Machine learning, deep learning and large language models are great tools to help make informed decisions, but they only give predicted values. In August 2023, Gartner published a hype cycle for emerging technologies. They placed generative AI at the peak of inflated expectations. This indicates there being a lot of hype and media attention around the product but limited proof that the innovation delivers what is needed or expected. Gartner predicted that a plateau would be reached in 2-5yrs. The plateau signifies users seeing real-world benefits leading to innovation going mainstream. Is the product truly worthy of hype - can we prove the product is trustworthy and reliable to be put into mainstream production? If so, how do we justify the hype? There is an element of uncertainty in a model's predictions. It is of interest to understand the model's reliability when making decisions. We can define uncertainty as the model's lack of confidence in its predictions. High uncertainty suggests that the model is not very confident whereas low uncertainty suggests high confidence.

“Statistics” as defined by the American Statistical Association (ASA) “is the science of learning from data, and of measuring, controlling and communicating uncertainty.”

Uncertainty quantification is thus quantitatively evaluating the degree of variability in the model's predictions. It focuses on quantifying the model's confidence in its outputs. In quantifying uncertainty different sources of error need to be distinguished.

Uncertainty quantification can be used to assess the risk associated with making different decisions based on the model predictions. Being able to quantify uncertainty gives insight into whether the model is overconfident and gives incorrect predictions with high certainty. Measuring uncertainty helps identify parts of the input space where the model performs poorly. This can be overcome by expanding the training data set. This would be epistemic uncertainty.

2. Quantifying Uncertainty

2.1 Types of Uncertainty

Two types of uncertainty exist: aleatoric and epistemic. Aleatoric uncertainty is due to randomness. It arises from noise in the data and cannot be reduced by adding more data. Epistemic uncertainty is due to a lack of knowledge. It represents limitations in the model's ability to fully capture the true distribution. Epistemic uncertainty can be reduced by increasing the data. Epistemic uncertainty can be formulated as a probability distribution over the model parameters. It has been postulated before that adding aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties together gives us total uncertainty. However, Wimmer (2023) argue and show that information theoretic measures may not be appropriate at disentangling aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties in classification and regression tasks.

2.2 Information Theory to Quantify Uncertainty

2.2.1 Information theory definitions

Entropy is the average or expected value of certainty in knowledge (information) of all possible outcomes of a random event.

Definition: The entropy of an event X with n possible outcomes and probabilities p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n is given by

$$H(X) = H(p_1, \dots, p_n) = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log(p_i)$$

Definition: The joint entropy $H(X, Y)$ of a pair of discrete random variables X and Y with a joint probability distribution $p(x, y)$ is given by

$$H(X, Y) = - \sum_{x \in X} \sum_{y \in Y} p(x, y) \log p(x, y)$$

Definition: The conditional entropy $H(Y|X)$ for discrete random variables X and Y is given by

$$H(Y|X) = - \sum_{x \in X} p(x) H(Y|X = x)$$

Definition: The chain rule for entropy is given by

$$H(X, Y) = - \sum_{x \in X} \sum_{y \in Y} p(x, y) \log p(x, y) = H(X) + H(Y|X)$$

2.2.2 Image caption generation

LLM image captioning models such as BLIP generate the caption one token at a time. Such models take an image input which passes through the encoder to obtain an encoded representation. This gets fed to the decoder along with [Decode] token to signal the beginning of the sequence. The decoder uses this to generate its own output in an encoded representation. This is passed through an output layer which contains linear layers. The linear layers output a score of the likelihood of occurrence of each word in the vocabulary set at each position in the output sequence. This is then passed through a softmax function to convert the scores into probabilities. To predict the output caption, one could simply take the highest probability at each position. This is Greedy Search and often produces the correct result. As each token is generated, the image and all previous tokens are considered.

When generating the next word in a sequence BLIP considers all the previous words generated (this is causal language modelling). The conditional probabilities for each word generated can be obtained from BLIP.

At each step of the caption generation process BLIP scores the full vocabulary set and selects the token with highest probability to be generated. So, if a caption with 12 tokens is generated then BLIP considers 12x30524 tokens to get the generated text. Xiao (2021) calculate entropy at the token-level and thus consider every possible outcome in the vocab set at each step. Most of the probabilities being summed are very close to 0. We thus set out to explore ways to calculate uncertainty at the sequence-level given the conditional probabilities from the BLIP model. Since there is no clear definition in how to do so, we can estimate entropy.

2.2.3 Our information theoretic measure

Consider an image captioning model that has vocabulary set \mathcal{V} . Let X_j be the j^{th} token of sequence with length n . Using the chain rule for entropy we can calculate the sequence entropy as

$$\begin{aligned} H(x_1^*, x_2^*, \dots, x_n^*) &= \sum_{j=1}^n H(x_j^* | x_{j-1}^*, x_{j-2}^*, \dots, x_1^*) \\ &= - \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} p(x_{i,j} | x_{j-1}^*, x_{j-2}^*, \dots, x_1^*, I) \log p(x_{i,j} | x_{j-1}^*, x_{j-2}^*, \dots, x_1^*, I) \end{aligned}$$

where I is the image, $x_{i,j}$ the i^{th} element in the vocabulary set for the j^{th} position in the sequence, x_j^* the j^{th} token generated in the sequence of length n (token with the highest conditional probability in the vocabulary set at position j).

Lakshminarayanan (2017) proposed the use of deep ensemble to quantify uncertainty. This a computationally less expensive than Bayesian methods and produces as good or better uncertainty estimates compared to Bayesian neural networks approximates.

Given M models in a deep ensemble, we define aleatoric uncertainty of the caption sequences to be

$$u_{al} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M H_m(x_1^*, x_2^*, \dots, x_n^*)$$

3. Empirical Study

The aim of this study is to assess the relationship between falsification, predictive uncertainty and complexity of captions in image captioning generation. We define falsification to be a generated word that is different from the ground truth. The complexity of the captions is determined by the length of the captions. An ensemble of BLIP image captioning models is used and we apply our information theoretic measure to quantify uncertainty.

3.1 Data

The UT Zappos50K data set is used. This is a large shoe data set containing 50,025 catalog images obtained from Zappos.com. Each shoe is centered on a white background and pictured in the same orientation. Different visual attributes of each shoe are stored in a metadata file.

Captions were created from the tabular data which for an n -length caption has form: "tag1 = value1, tag2 = value2, ..., tagn = valuen" where tag is the visual attribute and value is the associated value of the visual attribute for that image. This was done for ease of analysis and evaluation so that incorrect generations could easily be tracked.

3.2 Methods

The ensembles were formed in a similar manner as done in Katpally (2020). A bagging scheme was used with k -fold cross validation. Each fold was used to finetune a different model. The folds were

selected with replacement from the full training and test datasets. While bagging doesn't necessarily yield the best performance metrics, we are more interested in the methods of quantifying uncertainty.

The BLIP image captioning model was used to finetune the model to generate structured tag-value captions. In building the ensemble, four different models were used with different optimization functions and level of dropout. The ensemble combination is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Models in Ensemble

Fold/Model	Activation Function	Optimization Algorithm
1	GELU	AdamW
2	ReLU	AdamW
3	GELU	RMSProp
4	ReLU	RMSProp

An ensemble is created for each caption length. We do this by finetuning each model on the structured data of varying length.

Examples of data:

Image

Associated text:

Two tags: 'category = shoes, subcategory = oxfords'.

Four tags: 'category = shoes, subcategory = oxfords, closure = lace up, material = leather'.

Eight tags: 'category = shoes, subcategory = oxfords, heelheight = low, insole = leather ; memory foam ; removable, closure = lace up, gender = men, material = leather, toestyle = algonquin ; round toe ; closed toe'.

We end up with 12 models, 4 in each ensemble for the varying caption lengths.

3.3 Results

We collect results from the test dataset and get the average values from the ensemble which is show in Table 2. We use BLEU as our performance metric. This just looks for the number of matching n-grams between the ground truth and generated captions. We find that as caption length increases, the probability of falsification increases, aleatoric uncertainty increases and the performance measure decreases.

Table 2: Results for captions of differing lengths

Number of tags	Probability of Falsification	Aleatoric Uncertainty	BLEU Score
2	0.11	24.7258	0.9464
4	0.24	49.3496	0.8756
8	0.37	87.8136	0.8159

3.4 Results on Distribution Shift

Next we explore the case where our input distribution has changed. To change the distribution of the input we randomly apply gaussian noise to the images. We consider three levels of intensity: 0.1, 0.2, 0.5.

There is very little difference in change in aleatoric uncertainty when adding noise to images regardless of data complexity (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Aleatoric uncertainty for across different levels of noise added to images for different data complexities

The probability of falsification increases when more noise is added to an image. We observe this for the different data complexities (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Probability of falsification across different levels of noise for different data complexities

The performance measure, BLEU, decreases slightly when noise is added to images for the different data complexities (Figure 3).

Figure 3: BLEU across different levels of noise for different data complexities

4. Conclusion

There exist varying definitions of uncertainty and how uncertainty is decomposed into the aleatoric and epistemic parts. There is a lack of concrete definitions in image captioning, and this is what we set out to propose in terms of information theory. We found that longer captions had a greater probability of uncertainty and aleatoric uncertainty with a performance decrease. Adding differing levels of noise had little affect aleatoric uncertainty too much. More noise increases the probability of falsification and decreases performance. Further work is required to define epistemic uncertainty in image captioning.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my co-authors for their input and guidance in this work.

Thank you to the College of Computing and Software Engineering as well as the Graduate College at Kennesaw State University for the travel funding so that I could present my work here at JSM.

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